

Research Article

Assessment of Accumulation of Heavy Metals in Vegetables Irrigated with Water from Amba Stream in Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria¹Ishaleku, Y. Y., ^{1*}Etonihu, A. C. and ²Uzama, D.¹Department of Chemistry, Nasarawa State University, P.M.B 1022, Keffi, Nasarawa State.²Chemistry Advanced Research Centre, Sheda Science and Technology Complex, P.M.B. 186, Garki, Abuja. *Author for correspondence; Email: criseto@yahoo.com**Abstract**

Vegetable uptake of metals is one of the major pathways soil metals enter into the food chain and the subsequent bio-accumulated risks to human health when plant based food stuffs are consumed. This study assessed the impact of water from Amba Stream in Lafia, Nasarawa State used for irrigation. For the soil and sediment, the mean organic matter was 1.04 and 0.81% respectively. The mean pH of soil, sediment and water were 8.8, 7.1 and 6.9 respectively, while the moisture contents were 91.62 and 87.34% for soil and sediment, respectively. As expected, the soil sample had the highest concentrations of the heavy metals that ranged from 0.57 µg/g in Cd to 7.36 µg/g in Ni. The Amba stream water had higher levels of the heavy metals than the pipe-borne water used as a control, with the highest concentration of Cu (6.05 mg/l). The mean concentration of Cd in the stream water was 0.21 mg/l higher than the permissible level of 0.003 mg/l set by NAFDAC/NIS, while that in the sediments was not detected (ND). The results further showed that the concentrations of the metals were higher in the vegetables irrigated with water from the Amba stream than in the control except for Pb in spinach (0.01 µg/g) and As in water leaf (0.78 µg/g). Among the vegetables, bitter leaf had the highest concentration of Zn (3.94 µg/g) and Cu (5.09 µg/g). Arsenic (As) ranged from not detected in water leaf to 1.83 µg/g in pumpkin. Cd was not detected in all the vegetables. The bioconcentration factors in the irrigated vegetables were found to be highest for Zn but lowest for Pb in the order Zn (1.04) > Cu (0.89) > As (0.71) > Pb (0.02). Although the levels of the heavy metals in vegetables are quite below the phytotoxic level that posed no imminent danger to consumers, regular monitoring of levels of these metals in water used for irrigation is essential to prevent excessive build up of these metals in the food chain.

Keywords: Amba stream water, irrigation, heavy metals, vegetables.

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Introduction

Irrigated agriculture supports world growing population by increasing crop yield, offer employment, business opportunities and ameliorate the standard of living (Ani and Donye, 2005). However, the implications of irrigated agriculture are that lands no longer enjoyed fallow periods, increased salinity, soil erosion, compaction, and so on, thus generating the soil resource-base where remedial management practices are not instituted (Nwa, 1991; Agunwole *et al.*, 2001). Salinity favours the uptake of some metals by plants.

Sources of heavy metals contamination include atmospheric depositions, previous site used, use of metal garden container, paints, and burn fires. Through precipitation or ion exchange, heavy metals and their compounds enter into soil, water and plant ecosystem and thus, result in the accumulation or spread of heavy metals pollutants. Another important source of heavy metals are is liquid waste from metal galvanization, the tanning industry and other industries, sludge from sewage treatment plants, as well as municipal wastes. Unlike organic pollutant, they do not decay and thus pose a different kind of challenge for remediation and therefore calls for thorough researches on them. Large quantities of some heavy metals such as Cd and Hg enter the soil, and subsequently ground water and food chains through the extensive use of certain agrochemicals (Jakara, 2005).

The absorption of heavy metals by soil is regulated by a number of factors among which is pH and the organic matter content of the soil. When water from polluted sources is used for irrigation farming, it will eventually lead to increased level of heavy metal uptake by the crops and consequently endangering the human health (Abeh *et al.*, 2007). Plants grown on a land polluted with municipal, domestic or industrial wastes can absorb heavy metals in the form of mobile ions present in the soil solution through their roots or through foliar absorption. These absorbed metals get bio-accumulated in the roots, stems, fruits, grains and leaves of plants (Fatoki, 2000). When any of these plant parts are consumed by humans, it become hazardous particularly when the levels in the plant parts are well above tolerable limits as recommended by regulatory bodies such as WHO/FAO, NAFDAC, and SON. Another fact that is important is that, during rainy season, run offs from open contaminated sites, agricultural fields and even contaminated landfills, directly comes into streams and other water bodies (Vivek *et al.*, 2005).

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Vegetable uptake of metals is one of the major pathways soil metals enter into food chain and the subsequent bio-accumulated risks to human health when plant based food stuffs are consumed (Voussa *et al.*, 1996). The health risks depend on the chemical composition of the waste materials, its physical characteristics, the vegetables cultivated and the consumption rate (Khariah *et al.*, 1984). Generally, higher concentrations of trace metals are found in leafy vegetables and root crops than other types of vegetables (EPHC, 2003).

The aim of this study is to assess the impact of water from the river Amba in Lafia, Nasarawa State used for irrigation on the level of heavy metals in the vegetables, soil and sediment and to ascertain whether or not the consumption of these vegetables is safe for human consumption.

Materials and Methods

The Study Area

The study area is Lafia town, the headquarter of Lafia Local Government Area, and the capital of Nasarawa State. Lafia town is located between latitude 8,4833°E and longitude 8,5167°N and is bordered in the north by Lafia North Development Area, in the east by Lafia East Development Area, in the west by Doma Local Government Area and in the south by Obi Local Government Area. The town has a large land mass and a very large parcel of this land is reserved for residential development by the state government. A very good part of this land is also used as farmland. The population of the people in Lafia as at the last census is 330,712 (NPC, 2006) and most of the people are farmers, businessmen and civil servants.

Lafia is an ancient cosmopolitan town with an emirate rulership and the indigenes are mainly Kanuri, Jukun, Alago, Eggon, Gwandara, Koro, Akye, Rindre and Hausa/Fulani. The serene nature of the town that favours business activities, and also as the state capital, with so many machineries of government in place, have resulted to the increase in human population of the town. Consequently, wastes from homes, mechanic workshops, car wash, and the cottage industries empty into the stream.

Where are the environmental safety provisions? The safety provisions are not available, not used or misused. The water from Amba stream has been in use for irrigation of vegetables grown and consumed in Lafia town and its environs. Wastes from homes

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(domestic wastes), mechanic workshops, car wash, the cottage industries, etc empty into the stream.

Sampling

Sampling was done on vegetable farms along the length of the Amba stream. Five vegetable samples including spinach, pepper, pumpkin leaves, water leaves and bitter leaves were analyzed. Water and sediment samples were taken from points along the stream where water is pumped into the farm land. Soil samples were collected from the farm from points where the vegetables were uprooted. The sampling areas are shown in Figure 1.

Collection of Sediments and Water Samples

Water and the surface sediments of the stream were collected from the stream bank close to where water is being pumped into the farm lands. Water samples were collected using plastic containers, fetched from the designated points, mixed properly then, stored in a plastic container which had been rinsed with 0.01M HNO₃. Samples of sediments were collected by using plastic spoon to scoop from the designated points, mixed properly, air dried and ground in agate mortar and sieved to 63µm grain size and stored in a polythene bag until analysis.

Collection of Soil and Vegetable Samples

Soil samples were collected at each place from the Amba irrigation farms and at the time the vegetables were being uprooted. The soil samples were collected at 10 to 15 cm depth using hand auger then mixed thoroughly to give a representative fraction. The sample was air-dried ground and sieved using 200 µm mesh size and stored in polythene bag until analysis.

Five (5) irrigated vegetables comprising of leaves and fruits of spinach, bitter leaf, pumpkin, water leaf and pepper were collected. Random sampling of the vegetables was done when irrigation farming of vegetables was at its peak and in all the farms along the entire length of the stream used for irrigation. The harvested vegetables were thoroughly washed with distilled water, shredded and air-dried to avoid microbial degradation. After drying they were ground, sieved and packaged for analysis.

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Figure 1: Map of Lafia Town Showing Sample Location

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Control samples of the vegetables were obtained by planting similar seeds used by farmers on the same soil but watered with pipe borne water instead of the Amba stream water used by farmers for irrigation. Soil samples were taken randomly and were used to plant the seed using basket. These control vegetables were exposed to the same experimental conditions like the ones irrigated. When mature (after about three months of planting), the samples were harvested, thoroughly washed with distilled, shredded, sun dried, ground, sieved to 2 mm size and packaged in clean polythene leathers for analysis.

Determination of Physicochemical Parameters

pH and moisture content of the samples were determined according to the method of American Public Health Association (APHA, 1992) while organic matter was determined using the method of Verma (1994).

Heavy Metal Analysis

Zn, Cu, Cd, Pb, Ni and As were analyzed in the vegetables, soil, water and sediment samples by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (model AAS 969 Unicam Solar) using the method of APHA (1992).

Statistical Analysis

Statistical tools of mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation were used for analysis of the results.

Results and Discussion

Physicochemical Parameters of Stream Water, Soil and Sediment Samples

For the soil and sediment, the mean organic matter was 1.04 and 0.81% respectively. The mean pH for soil, sediment and water were 8.8, 7.1 and 6.9 respectively while the moisture contents were 91.62 and 87.34% for soil and sediment, respectively (Table 1). The pH of water is within the WHO/FAO recommended range of pH (6.50-9.50) for domestic and agricultural uses. pH of water is essential factor for maintaining appropriate composition of water. Water acidity is known to influence the solubility, availability and toxicity of metals in the aquatic ecosystems as well as in the soil.

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Table 1: Mean physical parameters of Amba stream water, soil and sediment samples

Sample	Organic matter (%)	pH	Moisture content (%)
Soil	1.04	8.8	91.62
Sediment	0.81	7.1	87.34
Stream Water	-	6.9	-

When the pH changes sharply, the biotic composition of water changes and the process of decomposition of organic materials of water reduce (Deepak, 2013). Organic matter is usually the organic fraction of decomposed plant and animal residues which plays important role in water retention, aggregation and soil structure. It effects to a large extent the availability or mobility of metal from soil to plant as well as soil fertility. Typical amount of organic matter in soil varies from <1% in ordinary soil to 90% in both peat soil and between 1% to 20% in mineral soils. Organic matter obtained in both sediments and soils were within this range. The relevance of organic matters to this study is its influence on the mobility and flux of metals. The normal range of organic matter obtained signified that metals in soil and sediment are bio-available since these metals are known to form complex with organic matter which influence their availability (Awofolu *et al.*, 2005). The moisture content of the sediment and soil are 87.34% and 91.62% respectively (Table 1). Moisture content is related to organic matter; it helps to improve soil structures as well as water and nutrient holding capacity, support soil microbes and protects soils, from erosion and competition.

The Concentration of Metals in Soil, Sediments and Stream Water

As expected, the soil sample had the highest concentrations of the heavy metals that ranged from 0.57 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in Cd to 7.36 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in Ni. The Amba stream water had higher levels of the heavy metals than the pipe-borne water used as control, with highest concentration of Cu (6.05 mg/l) (Table 2).

Table 2: Level of Metals in Stream water, Sediments and Soil

Pipe borne Metalswater	Stream water (mg/l)	Soil ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Sediment ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
Zn	0.002	3.28	3.78
Cu	0.005	6.05	5.71
Cd	ND	0.21	0.57
Pb	ND	0.57	1.60
Ni	ND	0.29	7.36
As	0.001	0.55	2.58

ND: Not Detected

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The level of zinc in stream water and sediments are 3.28 mg/l and 0.82µg/g, respectively. Nigeria Industrial Standard (NIS, 2007) permissible level of Zn in water is 3.00 mg/l, an indication that the water is contaminated and may cause detrimental effects. Based on this value, this stream water is not suitable for irrigation purposes (Awofolu *et al.*, 2005). The mean concentration of Cd in the stream water was 0.21 mg/l while that in the sediments was not detected (ND). This value of Cd is higher than the permissible level of 0.003 mg/l set by NAFDAC/NIS (2007). A similar higher concentration of Cd of 0.02 to 0.044 mg/l has been reported in the Tyume stream in South Africa (Awofolu *et al.*, 2005). Level of nickel in stream water and sediments are 0.29 mg/l and 1.45 µg/g, respectively. More attention has been focused on the toxicity of Ni in low concentration because certain Ni compounds may be carcinogenic (Awofolu *et al.*, 2005). Possible sources of Ni in surface water include anthropogenic sources, combustion of fossil fuels, (Awofolu *et al.*, 2005) old battery wastes, components of automobiles, old coins and many other items containing stainless steel and other nickel alloys. The levels of arsenic in stream water and sediments are 0.55 mg/l and 1.28µg/g, respectively. This value in water is higher than that set for water for domestic use. Ground, surface and drinking water are susceptible to arsenic poisoning resulting from the used of the multifarious activities such as environmental contaminants like pesticides, herbicides, insecticides, fungicides and animals feed additives (Awofolu *et al.*, 2005). The higher contents of As and Pb in this water could be due to their exposure to domestic and sewage dumps from nearby landfills, mechanic workshops and tannery cottages, especially along the stream. This is informative since this stream is commonly used for fishing and irrigation, thereby introducing high levels of Zn, Cu, Pb and As into the food chain.

Concentration of Metals in Vegetables

The mean concentrations of heavy metals in vegetable and control samples in the study area are listed in Tables 3 and 4.

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Table 3: Metal Levels in Vegetables Irrigated with Amba Stream Water ($\mu\text{g/g}$)

Vegetables								
Metal	Spinach	Water Leaf	Pumpkin	Pepper	Bitter Leaf	Mean	SD	CV%
Zn	3.25	1.19	3.45	1.13	3.94	2.59	1.33	51.4
Cu	3.73	3.29	3.84	3.44	5.09	3.88	0.71	18.3
Cd	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	NA	NA	NA
Pb	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.03	0.03	-	-
Ni	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	NA	NA	NA
As	0.78	ND	1.83	1.13	0.91	1.16	0.47	40.5

SD = Standard Deviation; CV% = Coefficient of variation percentage; ND = Not Detected; NA = Not Applicable

Table 4: Levels of Metals in the Control Vegetable Samples ($\mu\text{g/g}$)

Vegetables								
Metal	Spinach	Water Leaf	Pumpkin	Pepper	Bitter Leaf	Mean	SD	CV%
Zn	2.55	1.02	3.44	1.12	3.51	2.33	1.21	51.9
Cu	3.19	3.22	3.82	3.44	5.06	3.75	0.78	20.8
Cd	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	NA	NA	NA
Pb	0.01	ND	ND	ND	0.03	0.02	0.01	70
Ni	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	NA	NA	NA
As	ND	0.78	1.83	1.13	0.90	1.16	0.47	41

SD = Standard Deviation; CV% = Coefficient of variation percentage; ND = Not Detected; NA = Not Applicable

Tables 3 and 4 showed that the concentration of the metals were higher in the vegetables irrigated with water from the Amba stream than in the control except for Pb in spinach ($0.01\mu\text{g/g}$) and As in water leaf ($0.78\mu\text{g/g}$). Among the vegetables, bitter leaf had the highest concentration of Zn ($3.94\mu\text{g/g}$) and Cu ($5.09\mu\text{g/g}$). Arsenic (As) ranged from not detected in water leaf to $1.83\mu\text{g/g}$ in pumpkin. Cd was not detected in all the vegetables. These results agree with the earlier report that leafy vegetables have greater potential of accumulating heavy metals in edible part than fruity vegetables, grains or fruit crops (Mapanda *et al.*, 2007). From studies, it is evident that even the bioaccumulation of heavy metal in plants differs in the location and the type of metals and also the plant species. For instance, concentration of heavy metals in sunflower is greater in leaves and stem except for nickel that concentrates more in the seeds than any other part of the shoot (Dara, 1993). From studies on uptake of heavy metals by plants

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grown on garbage dumpsite, Pb accumulated in the leaves and roots of waterleaf while for okra it was in the fruits (Olawole, 2005). A similar work carried out by Alloway and Ayres (1997) showed that vegetables accumulate considerable amount of heavy metals (Pb, Cr, Cu, Zn) in roots and leaves. Vegetables do accumulate heavy metals in leaves, fruits, or both in leaves and roots. Root crops particularly, accumulate heavy metals in the roots and in some cases in the shoot system. Though copper and zinc are biologically essential, their excessive retention in the body cause adverse health effects (Maynard, 2000). In a study carried out to determine the concentration of heavy metals in some vegetable grown along motor high ways in Owerri, South Eastern Nigeria, it was discovered that the vehicular emissions and dumping of wastes on farmland contributed to high levels of heavy metals Pb, Mn, Cr, Zn, As, and Cd. From the study, Pb ranged from mean levels of 12.063 to 13.05 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in leaves of pumpkin (*Telferia occidentalis*) along Owerri/Onitsha highways, Mn in leaves of spinach (*Amaranthus cruetus*) and *Telferia occidentalis* ranged from 361.00 to 489.00 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 257.33 to 265.00 $\mu\text{g/g}$ along Owerri/Port Harcourt and Owerri/Aba high ways respectively, while Cd ranged from mean levels of 1.433 to 5.04 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in leaves of *Amaranthus cruetus* in all the highways (Alinor, 2008).

Bio-Concentration Factors

The bio-concentration factors are indications of the mechanism of uptake of these metals and their levels of accumulation (Adekanya, 1998). The bio-concentration factors in the irrigated vegetables were found to be highest for Zn but lowest for Pb in the order Zn (1.04) > Cu (0.89) > As (0.71) > Pb (0.02) (Table 5).

Table 5: The bio-concentration factors^a of the various metals in vegetable samples

Metal	Vegetables				
	Spinach	Water Leaf	Pumpkin	Pepper	Bitter Leaf
Zn	0.86	0.32	0.91	0.30	1.04
Cu	0.65	0.58	0.67	0.60	0.89
Cd	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Pb	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.02
Ni	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
As	0.30	NA	0.71	0.44	0.35

a = Ratio of concentration in vegetable ($\mu\text{g/g}$) to concentration in soil ($\mu\text{g/g}$); NA =Not Applicable

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Conclusion

The levels of metals in the sediment and soil are in relatively low concentration and within the acceptable limit recommended by WHO and NIS. The presence of Cd, Pb and Ni which usually contributes to the background concentration of the metals in the soil were not detected in the vegetables. There were slight differences in the vegetable samples with the irrigated vegetable sample accumulating the metals more than the control samples. This indicated a possible contribution from the stream water. However, the levels in vegetables are quite below the phytotoxic level and no imminent danger is posed to consumers. This study showed that water from the Amba stream used for irrigation increased the concentration of heavy metals in the farmland soil and eventual uptake by vegetables and their bioconcentrations. This has a long term effect that could constitute health risk to the populace consuming these vegetables. Consequently, regular monitoring of levels of these metals in waste water used for irrigation, irrigated vegetables and other food materials is essential to prevent excessive build up of these metals in the food chain.

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